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CARDIOVASCULAR RISK REDUCTION EFFECTS OF OMEGA-3 POLYUNSATURATED FATTY ACIDS IN FISH OIL AND KRILL OIL: A NETWORK META-ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Objective: Comparing the cardiovascular risk reduction effects of Omega-3 from fish oil and krill oil, considering various dosage forms. **Methods:** Adherence to the PRISMA 2015 checklist. Data were gathered from: Embase, PubMed, ClinicalTrials, ICTRP, and Cochrane, spanning from 1993 to 2023. Meta-analysis was performed on: Triglycerides (TG), Total Cholesterol (TC), High Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (HDL-C), Low Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (LDL-C) using R Version software: 2023.12.1+402. PROSPERO ID: CRD42024502338. **Results:** The study compared various interventions of fish oil (FO) including ethyl ester (EE), triglyceride (TG), re-esterified triglycerides (rTAG), and capsules (FO). Different types of krill oil (KO) including phospholipid/free fatty acid (PL/FFA), high concentration phospholipid (HPL), and low concentration phospholipid (LPL). The dose division per day: < 2: doses of (DHA+EPA) 300 - 1900 mg, < 3: doses of (DHA+EPA) 2000 - 3000 mg, > 3: doses of (DHA+EPA) exceeding 3000 mg. Meta-analysis results and treatment rankings (SUCRA, rankogram, league table) indicated that KO - PL/FFA < 3, FO - EE > 3, and FO - TG < 3 effectively reduce TG. FO - EE > 3, FO - rTAG < 2, FO-TG < 3 reduce TC. FO-TG < 3, FO < 3, FO < 2, KO - HPL < 2, KO < 2 increase HDL-C. FO - EE > 3, FO-EE < 2, FO - rTAG < 2 reduce LDL-C. Other interventions did not yield reliable results and were deemed ineffective. Only NMA LDL-C showed publication bias ($p = 0.0001 < 0.05$), while the other three variables demonstrated high reliability ($p > 0.05$), Egger's test. **Conclusion:** Most interventions are effective in reducing TG in cardiovascular patients, particularly KO - PL/FFA < 3. For cholesterol levels, using

FO - EE > 3 for positive effects on TC and LDL-C, FO - TG < 3 is beneficial through TC, TG and HDL-C, and FO - rTAG < 2 is effective in reducing TC and LDL-C.

Keywords: Fish oil, Krill oil, Cholesterol, Triglycerides, Unsaturated fatty acids, Cardiovascular disease.